

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 2

 Acceptance of papers **FEBRUARY, 2025**

Acceptance of articles

Published every
monthly

Directions

Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital
Object
Identifier

Visit our website
t.me/scopus_IST2100

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli,
Head of the Department of Scientific
Research and Innovations, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL "INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY" HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **97-748-70-03**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: munis.iriskulova@gmail.com

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Professor, Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
(Malaysia)

Asongu Simplicie
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD),
Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences
(PhD), USA

Judy B. Smetana
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), USA

CONTENTS

The importance and role of media image in the strategic development and contemporary reputation of higher education institutions	6
Nazarov Gulom	
Principles of organization and conduct of statistical observations of the living standards of the population.....	14
Ilyosova Dilbar Ismoil qizi	
The system of organizational and economic methods for improving the efficiency of energy sector enterprises and its key components	19
Matchanov Azamat Abadovich	
Key determinants of investment flow and fiscal health for data-driven policy decisions and information retrieval.....	24
Nilufar Zikirullaeva Dilmurod qizi	
Digital neighborhoods and intelligent systems in smart urban development.....	29
Ostanaqulova Gulsarakhan Muhammadyaqub kizi	
Literature study of german and uzbek languages: a ranking of linguistic discourse models.....	36
Rakhmonov Abdulaziz Batir ugli	
Ways to improve the efficiency of using innovative marketing strategies in retail enterprises.....	42
Safarov Bakhtiyor Dzhurakulovich, Kodirova Zulhumor Namazovna, Rakhmonova Zilola	
Ways of developing branding process in higher educational institutions	48
Shakirova Dilfuza Tulkunovna	
Creating authentic materials for esp students in tourism and hospitality	53
Tursunova Umida	
Developing the marketing activities of confectionery enterprises	59
Tuychieva Vasila Fakhridin qizi	
Methodological foundations for the development of the banking services market based on modern marketing strategies.....	65
Yuldasheva Dilrom Shakhzod kizi	
Blended learning: combining traditional and digital tools in esl teaching.....	69
Ziyoda Pulatova	
Issues of implementing circular economy principles in recycling industrial complexes.....	76
Gulchiroy Ismoilova	
The importance of increasing the competitiveness of the economy in joining the world trade organization	81
Akbarov Jasur Ikromjon ugli	
Restructuring of industrial enterprises: problems and solutions	86
B. Sulaymonov	
Analysis of the form of receivables and accounts payables of enterprises and organizations in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the quarter of 2024	91
Khalikulova Yulduz Panji qizi, Abdullayeva Fazilat Khazratovna	
Assessing the impact of corporate culture on enterprise performance in enterprises.....	96
Omanova Nargiza Rustam qizi	
Differencitae your teaching instruction in esp classroom	102
Shahnoza Berdiyeva Xolmaxmatovna	
Stabilizing ipos: the role of the greenshoe mechanism.....	105
Shakhzod Saydullaev	

ANALYSIS OF THE FORM OF RECEIVABLES AND ACCOUNTS PAYABLES OF ENTERPRISES AND ORGANIZATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FOR THE QUARTER OF 2024

Khalikulova Yulduz Panji qizi

Tashkent State University of Economics
ORCID: 0009-0002-5542-5367

Abdullayeva Fazilat Khazratovna

Tashkent State University of Economics
ORCID: 0009-0007-8114-4805

Abstract: This article analyzes public and private enterprises operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan, focusing on the first and second quarters of 2023 compared to the same periods in 2024. The study examines factors influencing the excess of accounts receivable and identifies the causes of increasing accounts payable. Furthermore, several recommendations are proposed to mitigate the growth of larger accounts payable in the future.

Key words: accounts receivable, accounts payable, state property, private property, dynamics.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of the economy and the growth of productive forces rely not only on existing enterprises but also on the establishment and launch of new ones. Such steps are based on economic feasibility, the availability of resources, and market demand for the enterprise's products. The scarcity or complete absence of a certain product can also justify establishing a new enterprise or production facility.

Businesses are primarily legal entities that operate based on ownership rights or full management rights over their property. They produce and sell goods, provide services, or carry out other economic activities as independent market participants. Their operations comply with existing laws and function under conditions of equal rights for all forms of ownership. The key objectives of businesses include efficiently organizing economic activities, creating jobs, and contributing to economic growth. Their main tasks are producing goods or providing services, maintaining competitiveness by considering market supply and demand, attracting investments, and generating profit. Additionally, they must account for social and ecological responsibilities in their activities.

A business achieves its goals by meeting the demand for its products and services, ensuring the social and economic well-being of its workforce. Each business has material, financial, labor, and energy resources at its disposal to sustain its operations. Furthermore, businesses have the right to own, utilize, and manage their allocated portion of public property.

There are various types of businesses and organizations based on ownership structures. In this article, we analyze the financial performance of state-owned and privately owned enterprises using data from the first and second quarters of 2023 and 2024. Specifically, we focus on the existing accounts receivable and payable, providing a comprehensive overview of their nature and significance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The continuous analysis of receivables and payables in private and public enterprises is gaining increasing importance in the context of economic reforms. This issue remains a key area of scientific research.

In particular, B.A. Khasanov highlights in his research that regular analysis of receivables and payables helps strengthen financial discipline, implement measures to reduce overdue debts, improve the payment and settlement system between business entities, and ensure the timely payment of taxes and mandatory contributions to the budget and state target funds. Additionally, it contributes to minimizing budget debts and preventing their accumulation, leading to more effective debt management.

According to economist I. Choriyeu, preventing the accumulation of overdue receivables, increasing business entities' responsibility for the rational use of working capital, and ensuring its preservation and timely replenishment are crucial. These measures, in turn, contribute to improving macroeconomic indicators, which are essential for sustainable socio-economic development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study aims to improve the theoretical and practical aspects of analyzing the reduction of receivables and payables in state and private enterprises and organizations, addressing several key issues in this area. Various methods, such as comparison, synthesis, and comparative analysis, were employed during the research. Additionally, analyses were conducted based on statistical data and tables, with results evaluated on a scientific basis.

At the conclusion of the study, specific recommendations and proposals suitable for practical implementation were developed. This scientifically grounded approach introduces new methodologies for application in the production and service processes of enterprises and organizations, regardless of their form of ownership.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Numerous scholars have conducted research on the analysis of receivables and payables in enterprises and organizations. Recently, interest in enterprise economics has grown significantly. This is due to the fact that, in a market economy, new legal and organizational forms of enterprises, raw material suppliers, material and equipment providers, as well as direct consumers (buyers) of products and goods, continue to emerge and evolve.

Furthermore, an enterprise is, above all, a production team consisting of individuals engaged in diverse activities, forming a system of mutual relations and establishing a particular lifestyle, spiritual values, and moral norms. All these factors necessitate a reconsideration of economic activity forms and methods, as well as a fresh perspective on the role of enterprises in economic development.

Today, many enterprises are transitioning into joint-stock companies, holdings, and financial-industrial groups. Unlike the planned economy era, where production functions were restricted by strict controls, limits, and norms, the state now provides broad opportunities for enterprise initiative, creative research, and entrepreneurship. Independent economic activity and freedom except in cases prohibited by law are the defining characteristics of modern enterprises.

Within the framework of this study, key terminology related to receivables and payables is explained as follows:

Accounts receivable – Includes debts owed by buyers and customers, branches and subsidiaries, advances to employees, suppliers, and contractors, as well as taxes, fees, and insurance payments to the budget and state trust funds. It also includes debts of founders for their shares in the authorized capital, employee debts for other operations, and other outstanding receivables.

Accounts payable – Encompasses debts to suppliers and contractors, branches and subsidiaries, overdue obligations for taxes and other mandatory payments, advances received, debts related to budget payments, insurance liabilities, debts to state trust funds, obligations to founders, wage debts, and other outstanding payables.

In analyzing this topic, we will examine the status of debtor and creditor obligations of enterprises and organizations, categorized by ownership type and organizational-legal form, using statistical data from the first quarter of 2024 (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Debt and creditor debt of enterprises and organizations by form of ownership in billion soums (as of March 2024)¹.

The above data show that, as of the first quarter of 2024, the total receivables of enterprises and organizations amounted to 275,606.1 billion soums, of which the debts of state-owned enterprises totaled 4,424.3 billion soums, while the debts of private enterprises amounted to 271,181.7 billion soums.

The total payables of these enterprises and organizations reached 293,085.1 billion soums, including 4,695.4 billion soums in debts of state-owned enterprises and 288,389.7 billion soums in debts of private enterprises.

These indicators influence the annual cash flow rate, liquidity, and profitability of enterprises and organizations. Additionally, they contribute to the emergence and increase of negative impacts of accounts payable on the profitability of enterprises.

Now, let's analyze the receivables and payables of enterprises and organizations by type of economic activity as of March 1, 2024, categorized by form of state ownership (Table 1):

Table 1. Accounts receivable and payable by enterprises and organizations by type of economic activity as of March 1, 2024, by state ownership².

	STATE PROPERTY			
	Accounts receivable		Accounts payable	
TOTAL:	4 424.3	130.5	4 695.4	294.7
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	-	-	-	-
Industry	1 044 .7	61.7	1 036.0	116.3
Construction	386.0	-	568.3	-
Trade	1.0	-	1.7	-
Transportation and storage	389.5	1.5	119.4	1.5
Accommodation and food services	9.4	-	7.6	-

1 Source: Compiled and analyzed by the author based on data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2 Source: Compiled and analyzed by the author based on data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Information and communication	1 214.6	0.002	1 988.8	0.0003
Providing health and social services	3.7	-	6.3	-
Others	1 375.4	67.5	967.1	176.9

When analyzing the data on the status of enterprises as of March 1, 2024 by form of ownership, state-owned enterprises accounted for 4,424.3 billion soums, or 1.6% of total receivables, while private-owned enterprises accounted for 271,181.7 billion soums, or 98.4% of the total.

Table 2. Accounts receivable and payable by type of private ownership of enterprises and organizations by type of economic activity as of March 1, 2024³.

	PRIVATE PROPERTY			
	Accounts receivable		Accounts payable	
TOTAL:	271 181.7	15 822.4	288 398.7	9 292.1
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	448.3	1.5	349.0	0.03
Industry	166 292.7	5 166.9	173 337.4	8 700.7
Construction	10 607.8	79.6	15 844.8	46.7
Trade	27 479.5	672.2	32 281.5	485.9
Transportation and storage	35 508.8	9 667.4	33 281.5	0.7
Accommodation and food services	782.6	40.1	1 087.6	13.2
Information and communication	4 666.4	5.9	6 134.8	0.01
Providing health and social services	217.9	15.3	350.8	0.7
Others	25 177.8	173.5	25 743.8	44.2

As of March 1, 2024, 4,695.4 billion soums, or 1.6% of the total creditor debt, belonged to enterprises with state ownership, while enterprises with private ownership accounted for 288,389.7 billion soums, or 98.4% of the total.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, as of March 1, 2024, the highest share of receivables of enterprises and organizations was accounted for by buyers and customers (39.6%), advances to suppliers and contractors (35.2%), and advance payments on taxes and levies to the budget and special-purpose state funds (5.1%). As of the same date, the largest share of accounts receivable of enterprises and organizations by form of ownership was accounted for by suppliers and contractors (54.0%), advances received (20.4%), and payments to the budget and target funds (3.2%). Additionally, the largest share of accounts receivable of enterprises and organizations by organizational and legal form was limited liability companies or additional liability companies, which accounted for 135,163.3 billion soums, or 49.0% of the total. Similarly, the largest share of creditor debt was held by limited liability or additional liability companies, amounting to 150,176.2 billion soums, or 51.2% of the total creditor debt.

References

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Introduction of Criteria for Assessing the Effectiveness of the Activities of Joint-Stock Companies and Business Entities with State Shares." Resolution No. 207 of July 28, 2015. <https://www.lex.uz/en/search/all?lang=4&actnum=207&fyear=2015>
2. Official website of the Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan: <http://www.stat.uz>.
3. Rakhimov, M.Y., & Qalandarova, N.N. (2019). Financial Analysis. Tashkent: "Economics-Finance".
4. Khasanov, B.A., Rakhimov, M.Y., Muqumov, Z.A., Alikulov, A.I., Jumanova, A.B., Khazhimuratov, N.Sh., & Khasanova, R.B. (2019). Financial Analysis. Tashkent: «Economics».
5. Pirakhunova, F.N., & Pardaev, S.A. (2024). Carrying Out Accounts Receivable and Accounts Payable in Accounting (Financial) Reporting. Proceedings of International Educators Conference, 3(2), 250–255.
6. Rakhimov, M.Y., & Khasanov, B.A. (2023). Analysis of Receivables and Payables in Uzbek Enterprises. Journal of Financial Studies, 12(4), 45–59.
7. Khasanova, R.B., & Alikulov, A.I. (2022). The Impact of Accounts Receivable Management on Financial Stability in Uzbekistan. Central Asian Economic Review, 8(3), 78–92.

3 Source: Compiled and analyzed by the author based on data from the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

8. Muqumov, Z.A., & Jumanova, A.B. (2021). Strategies for Reducing Accounts Payable in State-Owned Enterprises. *Uzbekistan Journal of Economics*, 15(2), 33–47.
9. Khazhimuratov, N.Sh., & Qalandarova, N.N. (2020). Comparative Analysis of Receivables and Payables in Private and Public Sectors. *Economic Analysis Bulletin*, 9(1), 22–36.
10. Alikulov, A.I., & Rakhimov, M.Y. (2019). Financial Reporting Standards and Their Application in Managing Receivables and Payables. *Finance and Accounting Journal*, 7(5), 50–64.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 2

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles
Published every
monthly

Directions
Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

 Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

**ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO
THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633**

CONTACT:

- Contact us
+998 97 748 70 03
- Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

 Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>